

Metallurgical characterization of two 11th-12th c. single-bow shears from Sigtuna, Sweden

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Abstract

Shears, being everyday objects, have received significantly less attention by archaeometallurgists than other edged tools or weapons. Yet, shear blades were forged with the same techniques as blades of e.g. knives and swords. The most common shear type in ancient times was the bow shears, where the bow had to be flexible so it could be repeatedly bent without cracking or breaking. The shear-maker therefore faced the challenge of combining hard steel (the blades) with soft/flexible steel (the bow). In fact, bow shears are one of the first tools to be invented where metal acts as a spring. Thus, ancient bow shears can be used for investigating the history and development of spring steel technology, which currently is unclear. Here, we present the metallurgical characterization of two 11th – 12th c. single bow shears from Sigtuna, Sweden. Both the blades and the bows of the two shears were found to be of decent quality, and much better than in older shears from the Roman period. Although the steel qualities are not quite up to modern standards, this does not in itself prove that the Sigtuna blacksmiths lacked the technological knowledge to make ideal spring steel. Shears are relatively cheap everyday objects intended to be used until they break, at which point they are discarded. Therefore, it might not have been worth the Medieval blacksmiths' time and effort to perfect the material properties of steel used in shears. The shears' blades are on par with Medieval period knife blades, and future studies on ancient shear-making should preferably involve comparisons of shears and knives from the same origins.

1. Introduction

Shears and scissors are today present in virtually every household. They come in different types and designs, all of which evolved from the single-bow shears invented in ancient Babylon or Egypt (Notis and Shugar, 2003; Wiss, 1948). In modern times the most popular type is the hinged scissors, which likely were developed during the Graeco-Roman period (Notis and Shugar, 2003). Bow shears are however still in use for specific purposes such as sheep shearing. The typical design and terminology of Medieval single bow shears and their parts are shown in Fig. 1. The principal parts are the bow and the arms, which together constitute the handle, and the blades, which have edges that end in tips.

Shears are relatively common finds at archaeological sites, but they are considered everyday objects and comparatively under-researched (Goodall, 1990; Hansen et al., 2015). Blades and edges of swords, axes, and in particular knives (Zavjalov and Terekhova, in press) have received significantly more metallurgical attention than the blades and edges of shears, even though the latter are produced with similar techniques. Bow shears feature another part that is challenging to forge, namely the bow, which typically is the first part to break. A good shear bow must remain strong and flexible even after many cycles of repeated use. In fact, the bow shears were likely one of the first tools to be developed that involved metal acting as a spring. The history of spring steel technology is unclear (Wells, 1973), and somewhat difficult to research as many grades of iron/steel can be treated to become suitable spring material. So far, only a handful of ancient shears have been investigated, mainly dating to the Iron Age. These studies reveal how the smiths struggled to solve the problem of crafting a tool that involves one very flexible part, i.e. the bow, situated between two very inflexible parts, i.e. the blades (Gaitzsch, 1980; Notis and Shugar, 2003; Piaskowski, 1961, 1966; Pleiner, 1959; Shugar et al., 2006). There are very few studies of shears from later periods. Wilthew (2000) compared knives and shears from Medieval London, but studied only the blades and did not present images of microstructures.

Here, we present the metallurgical analysis of two 11th- 12th c. single bow shears, encountered in central Sigtuna during research excavations in AD 1988 – 1999. Sigtuna was central Sweden's administrative centre for the early Medieval kings, and the town contained numerous craftspeople and artisans (Croix et al., 2019; Tesch, 1990). Sigtuna's archaeological record consequently includes several workshops with an abundance of crafting tools and raw materials. Many studies have used Sigtuna's rich archaeological material to investigate Swedish crafting technology during the Viking Age and early Medieval periods (Edberg, 2013; Pettersson, 2007; Sjöbeck, 2016; Söderberg, 2006, 2011; Söderberg and Gustafsson, 2007; Tesch, 1990; Wärmländer and Söderberg, 2019). In line with our previous studies of Scandinavian iron working in the Viking Age and Medieval periods (Helén et al., 2021; Wärmländer et al., 2018; Wärmländer et al., 2010), the overall aim of the current study is to characterize the techniques involved in crafting the two shears, and in particular to find out how well the material properties of the shears' different parts correspond to their intended functions.

2. Materials

The two investigated single-bow shears are made from iron/steel and display fully looped bows (Fig. 2). They were encountered in trenches 9 and 10 during the 1988 – 1999 research excavations of the block Trädgårdsmästaren in central Sigtuna, Sweden. They have been stratigraphically dated to the 11th – 12th centuries, and are currently curated at the Sigtuna museum with inventory numbers 27182 (shears-1) and 23276 (shears-2). Both shears have undergone conservation treatment involving removal of surface corrosion, followed by coating with wax to reduce further corrosion. Shears-1 is the smaller one, around 12 cm long, with the bow broken and both blades bent (Fig. 2). Shears-2 is thicker and longer, i.e. around 21 cm in total length. It is three times broken: in the bow, in one of the arms, and in the opposite blade. The last two breaks exhibit very little corrosion, suggesting that they occurred during or after the excavation. The break in the bow is heavily corroded, and thus likely happened before shears-2 were deposited in the ground.

3. Methods

Samples from the two shears were cut with a Discotom-2 metallurgical cutting machine (Struers ApS, Denmark) and mounted either in Epoxicure resin (Buehler Inc., USA) or in conductive PolyFast resin (Struers ApS, Denmark). After grinding and polishing – the final step with 1 μm diamond paste – the samples were etched with 2% - 4% Nital solution for 10 - 20 sec, and then examined in a Leica DMRM metallurgical microscope (Leica Camera AG, Germany). The hardness of different metallurgical phases was tested with a MXT CX-1 micro-Vickers indenter (Matsuzawa Co. Ltd, Japan) using a load of 200 gf. A CCD video camera (SSC-DC38P; Sony Co., Japan) and Leica's QWin v.3 software was used to record microstructure photographs and to calculate Vickers hardness (HV_{200}) values. Based on the microstructure images, carbon content was estimated manually via grid analysis, assuming zero carbon in ferrite and 0.67 % carbon in pearlite. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) was carried out using a table-top TM-3000 SEM unit (Hitachi Ltd., Japan) operating at 15 kV.

4. Results

4.1 Shears-1 (#27182)

Microstructure photographs of samples from the bow and one arm of shears-1 are presented in Fig. 3. Both the arm (Fig. 3A) and the bow (Fig. 3C) consist mainly of ferrite, but the grain size in the arm is smaller (around 50 μm) than in the bow (around 100 – 200 μm). The larger grain size in the bow (Fig. 3C) shows that this part was subjected to a rather high temperature and then grain growth occurred after recrystallization. The ferrite grains in the bow region closer to the arm are smaller and display deformation-elongation from intentional working of the material (Fig. 3D). For the arm sample, occasional stringers are present that could be silica flux (Fig. 3A). In a region close to the arm surface some pearlite is present, and the ferrite grains display Widmanstätten structure created by rapid cooling (Fig. 3B).

Microstructure photographs of samples from one of the blades of shears-1 are presented in Fig. 4. The blade has a sandwich structure (Figs. 4A and 4B), with two outer carburized layers around a core of pure ferrite. This ferritic core displays grain sizes in the range 40-80 μm (Fig. 4C) and extends to the back of the blade (Fig. 4B), indicating that the blade was made from different pieces of iron forged together. The two carburized regions contain several longitudinal stringers, which most likely consist of silica flux material (Fig. 4A). Otherwise, these regions are relatively homogeneous. The material in the carburized regions consists of approximately 17 % pearlite and 83 % ferrite (Fig. 4D), which corresponds to an estimated carbon content of around 0.14 %. The grains in the carburized regions are smaller, i.e. around 10-30 μm (Figs. 4A; 4B; 4D), indicating work-hardening and recrystallization. Hardness measurements of the blade returned an average HV_{200} value of 132 for the ferrite core, while the carburized edges are much harder, i.e. around 209 HV_{200} . SEM-EDS analysis was not able to detect any metals other than iron in the samples from shears-1 (data not shown).

4.2 Shears-2 (#23276)

Microstructure photographs of samples from the bow, one of the arms, and one of the blades of shears-2 are presented in Fig. 5. An SEM image of the blade sample is shown in Fig. 6. The bow and the examined arm of shears-2 are both display relatively heterogeneous microstructures (Figs. 5A and 5C), consisting of small-grained (20 - 30 μm) rather pure ferrite (bright grains) interspersed with patches of a combination of pearlite/ferrite (dark grains). Some silicon-based inclusions are also present (Fig. 5A). In the mixed pearlite/ferrite structure in the arm, where the grains are around 20 – 50 μm across, the ferrite is present mainly at the grain boundaries as a pointy Widmanstätten structure, caused by rapid cooling (Fig. 5B). The composition seems to be around 76 % pearlite to 24 % ferrite, which corresponds to a carbon content of around 0.5 %. The blade (Fig. 5D) consists almost entirely of martensite, together with occasional grains of ferrite and pearlite and small amounts of silicon-based inclusions. These inclusions are not very elongated, which means that they have not

been extensively worked (Figs. 5D and 6). SEM-EDS analysis showed that the inclusions consist mainly of Si, together with some Al, Ca, K, and O (Table 1). This would be a common composition for both slag inclusions and added silica flux (i.e., sand), and we can therefore not determine the exact nature of these inclusions. The amounts of Fe measured in the inclusions may originate from the surrounding iron. The SEM-EDS analysis furthermore did not reveal any trace elements in the blade - in particular no Mn or P (Table 1). Hardness measurements produced average HV₂₀₀ values of 890 for the martensitic phases in the blade, and values of 240 and 105 for the pearlitic and ferritic phases in the arm. The region next to the break in the bow was completely corroded and thus impossible to sample for microstructure analysis. The overall analytical results for both shears-1 and shears -2 are summarized in Table 2.

5. Discussion

Both shears consist of pure, non-alloyed iron with a low slag content. The amount of carbon is very low, which is typical for iron produced with the bloomery furnace (Buchwald, 2008; Magnusson, 1986). However, as the shears date to the 11th – 12th c. and as the blast furnace was introduced in Sweden around the 12th – 13th c. (Buchwald, 2008), it is possible that the shears might have been produced with iron from a blast furnace, such as osmund iron (Helén et al., 2021; Wallander, 2018). Both shears display broken bows, which probably is why they were discarded. This suggests that shears were not objects of very high value in Medieval Sigtuna, a major town with several large-scale crafting workshops (Karlsson, 2016; Tesch, 1990). At a remote farmstead on the other hand, where obtaining and forging iron objects likely was less convenient, metal items were likely recycled (Wärmländer et al., 2010), and broken shears might have been repaired or remodelled into knives. Although the two shears studied here are of a similar type, their material properties are different.

Shears-1 are made from two materials: a ferritic material that forms the basis of the shears, and a carburized material forge-welded around the ferritic blade cores (Figs. 4A and 4B). Such a lamellar design provides good overall material properties and is sometimes seen for knife blades from the Viking and Medieval periods (Cowgill et al.,

2000; Peets, 2003; Tylecote, 1990; Wärmländer et al., 2010). However, the reverse design with ferritic materials sandwiching a steel core should be preferred (Tylecote, 1990; Zavyalov and Terekhova, in press). In Tylecote's (1990) words, the drawback of folding steel around a ferrite core is that the "steel edge will wear away with sharpening until eventually there is no steel left and the knife becomes useless and is discarded". Perhaps such a design is more suitable for shears, where the bow might break before the edge has been sharpened down to the ferritic core. The longitudinal stringers observed in the carburized region are likely silica flux material (Fig. 4A), possibly added while folding the material during carburization, which likely is how the homogenous carbon distribution was achieved. The careful forge-welding of the carburized material to the ferritic core has produced a blade with overall good material qualities, although the hardness of the work-hardened pearlite + ferrite (HV₂₀₀ around 210; Table 2) is at the low end for shear blades: these edges would need constant re-whetting to maintain their sharpness. The Widmanstätten ferrite in the arm sample (Fig. 3B) suggests treatment with rapid cooling, perhaps in a failed attempt to create harder martensitic blades? But this is only a speculation, and martensite with a carbon content of 0.14 % is not very hard.

The bow of shears-1 is made from pure large-grain ferrite (Fig. 3C), with some grain deformation present in the region next to the arm (Fig. 3D). Such deformation increases the tensile strength and thus the elasticity of the ferrite. Work-hardened ferrite is therefore an ideal material for resisting cyclic deformation, as the crystal structure is not sensitive to fatigue/cyclic stress. However, a somewhat smaller grain size would be preferred, as large grains have lower tensile strength and are more prone to cracking. Also, combining the ferrite with some harder pearlite would increase the overall strength of the material. Yet, this bow consists of relatively good spring material. It is unclear to what extent this is intentional. Forging a bow to shape requires at least a few cycles of working and annealing/normalizing, i.e. heat-treatment to reduce the tension in the material induced by the work cycles. Was the work deformation of the bow seen in Fig. 3D done on purpose to improve the bow's elasticity, or is it merely a result of less careful heat-treatment after the bow had

received its shape? Also, did the blacksmith intentionally remove the carbon from the ferritic bow region, or was the material carbon-free from the beginning?

Shears-2 is made from a heterogeneous low-carbon material. The relatively pure martensite in the blades (Fig. 5D) makes them appropriately strong, i.e. a HV_{200} around 890 (Table 2). These large shears should therefore have been able to cut not only hair and fabric, but also objects like small twigs, and could be used for a long period without need for re-sharpening. Combined with the absence of cementite and zig-zag-patterns, the fine lamellar structure and high hardness of the martensite suggest a medium carbon concentration in the blade, perhaps around 0.4 – 0.5 % (Fig. 5D). This might indicate intentional carburization, perhaps carried out in the forge. Some carbon gradients are present in the arms and in the bow, where the patches of pearlite in the small-grained ferrite strengthen the material (Figs. 5A-5C). This combination of ferrite and pearlite would actually have been rather good bow material, almost up to modern standards, had it not been for the pointy Widmanstätten microstructure of the ferrite grains (Fig. 5B): sharp edge structures are never good for the overall material quality. The Widmanstätten ferrite (Fig. 5B) shows that the bow was quenched, just like the arm (Fig. 5D) - perhaps the entire object was quenched when the blade martensite was created. Fig. 5C shows a crack between a pearlitic and a ferritic region in the bow of shears-2. Here, two different materials were probably forged together. Such a combination is not ideal as bow material, as the difference in hardness between the two regions easily leads to crack formation when the bow is bent. On a related note, the reason why the bow now is completely corroded in the region where it broke is likely related to fatigue corrosion, which acts in the micro-cracks caused by repeated bending.

Our analyses combined together show that the two shears were forged with decent craftsmanship. Ideal shears should combine a flexible bow with hard martensitic blade edges, where the latter preferably should contain some carbon for increased hardness and possibly be combined with softer ferritic layers to resist cracking. The blades of shears-2 are made from hard martensite, and appear to be on par with Medieval knife

blades, which typically are of a good quality even though there can be some variation in material composition (Cowgill et al., 2000; Peets, 2003; Tylecote, 1990). For shears-1, the blade edges are made from pearlite + ferrite rather than martensite. This could be an intentional design that might be suitable for smaller shears with thin blades. Further research might clarify if Medieval shears could have been crafted according to different design schemes, with intentional differences in material design based on e.g. the size and/or intended use of the shears. As expected, the blades of the two Sigtuna shears are of higher quality than Roman period shear blades, which typically were made from martensite mixed with various other phases but not from pure martensite (Gaitsch, 1980; Notis and Shugar, 2003; Piaskowski, 1961). This is consistent with the general metallurgical improvements over time of bladed objects. By the Medieval period, the best smiths clearly knew how to craft axes, knives, and swords with blades of almost perfect material quality. The blades of shears-1 and shears-2 are not perfect, but that does not necessarily mean that the Sigtuna blacksmiths lacked technological skill or knowledge. Instead, as shears are everyday objects that will be used until they break, it might not have been worth the extra time and effort to work shear blades into perfection.

The same reasoning can be applied to the bows of shears-1 and shears-2, which are of decent but not perfect quality, as described above. However, even if the Sigtuna blacksmiths had the skill to make perfect spring steel for the bows, it might not have been worth the effort, just like for the blades. From that point of view, investigating everyday objects such as shears might not say much about state-of-the-art technology. On the other hand, as the bow is the part of the shears that typically breaks first, it is also the part most in need of improvement. Unfortunately, we are not aware of any metallurgical studies of Medieval spring iron/steel (in shears or other objects) to which the current results can be compared. Roman period shear bows were sometimes made from bronze, and sometimes made from ferritic iron (Notis and Shugar, 2003). The bronze bows had to be riveted to the iron arms, and sometimes also, the iron bows were riveted: Roman Age blacksmiths were apparently not always comfortable with forging single-piece shears. Both Sigtuna shears are single-piece objects, and the

forge-welding of the carburized material to the blades in shears-1 is clearly a more efficient way of combining two materials than riveting. The fully looped bows (C-shape) of the Sigtuna shears furthermore provide more efficient elastic properties than the simple U-shaped loop that sometimes is found in Roman period shears (Goodall et al., 1984; Notis and Shugar, 2003). Yet, even though it appears that there are significant differences/improvements between Roman period shears and Medieval shears, the two shears studied here can of course not represent the entirety of Medieval shear-making. Clearly, more research needs to be done on the history and development of bow shears and spring steel technology, both for the Medieval and for other time periods.

Another subject requiring further investigation is how the Sigtuna smiths carburized their iron. Ethnographic descriptions indicate that 18th c. Scandinavian blacksmiths were able to carburize iron to steel in a forge hearth, allowing carbon from the charcoal fuel to diffuse into the surface of the iron bar (Evenstad, 1790, 1968; Rinman, 1782; Swedenborg, 1923; Wagner, 1990). Such traditional techniques might have been known already in the Medieval period. In continental Europe, Theophilus' 12th c. crafting treatise "On Various Arts" (Hawthorne and Smith, 1979) describes two methods for carburizing iron, both of which involve applying carbon-rich materials to the iron surface. The first method is to sprinkle ash from oxen horns mixed with salt over the iron bar while forging it. The second is to smear the bar with pig's fat, wrap it in linen and leather, and heat the package in the forge. It appears likely that similar methods would have been known also in Scandinavia. A related question, for future research, is if the Medieval Scandinavian blacksmiths had procedures for de-carburizing iron in the forge.

6. Conclusions

Our analyses of the two single-piece bow shears from Medieval Sigtuna, Sweden, show that the blacksmiths had crafted both the blades and the bows with decent but not perfect material quality. This could be related to the shears being everyday objects, intended to be used until breaking and then discarded. As expected, the two

Medieval shears display better design, workmanship, and material quality than Roman period shears (Goodall et al., 1984; Notis and Shugar, 2003). Little is known about the historical development of spring steel technology, and analysis of bow shears from different time periods might be useful in clarifying this development. The studied shear blades display similar structures as Medieval knife blades, and future studies of ancient bow shears could benefit from including metallurgical comparisons with knives from similar origins.

Bibliography

- Buchwald, V.F., 2008. Iron, Steel and Cast iron before Bessemer. The Royal Danish Academy of Science and Letters, Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Cowgill, J., de Neergaard, M., Griffiths, N., 2000. Knives and Scabbards. The Boydell Press, Woodbridge, U.K.
- Croix, S., Neiß, M., Sindbæk, S.M., 2019. The réseau opératoire of Urbanization: Craft Collaborations and Organization in an Early Medieval Workshop in Ribe, Denmark. *Cambridge Archaeological Journal* 29, 1-20.
- Edberg, R., 2013. Ett nitjärn från Sigtunas vikingatid. *Situne Dei*, 71-74.
- Evenstad, O., 1790. Afhandling om Jern-Malm, som findes i Myrer og Moradser i Norge, og Omgangsmåden med at forvandle den til Jern og Staal. Kgl. Danske Landhuusholdnings-selskab, Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Evenstad, O., 1968. A treatise on iron ore as found in the bogs and swamps of Norway and the process of turning it into iron and steel. Abridged translation of Evenstad 1790 by Niels L. Jensen. *Bulletin of the Historical Metallurgy Group* 2, 61-65.
- Gaitzsch, W., 1980. Eiserne Römische Werkzeuge. Section 16 in *BAR International Series* 78.
- Goodall, I.H., 1990. Shears and scissors, in: Biddle, M. (Ed.), *Object and Economy in Medieval Winchester*. Oxford University Press, U.K.
- Goodall, I.H., Ellis, B., Gilmour, B., 1984. Iron Objects, in: Rogerson, A., Dallas, C. (Eds.), *Excavations in Thetford 1948-59 and 1973-80, East Anglian Report* 22, Gressenhall, U.K.
- Hansen, G., Ashby, S.P., Baug, I., 2015. *Everyday Products in the Middle Ages*. Oxbow Books, Oxford, UK.
- Hawthorne, J.G., Smith, C.S., 1979. *Teophilus: On Divers Arts* (translated from latin). Dover Publications, New York.
- Helén, A., Hansson, J., Karlsson, C., Wallander, A., Magnusson, G., Eliasson, A., Wärmländer, S.K.T.S., 2021. Ett skepp kommer lastat: metallurgisk identifiering av osmundjärn funnet i ett skeppsvrak från 1500-talet i Stockholms skärgård. *Fornvännen* 116, 74-77.
- Karlsson, J., 2016. *Spill - om djur, hantverk och nätverk i mälarområdet under vikingatid och medeltid*. Stockholm University, Stockholm.
- Magnusson, G., 1986. Bloomery iron production in the county of Jämtland, Sweden. *Jernkontoret*, Stockholm, Sweden.
- Notis, M.R., Shugar, A.N., 2003. Roman shears: Metallography, composition, and a historical approach to investigation, *Archaeometallurgy in Europe*. Associazione Italiana di Metallurgia, Milan, Italy, pp. 109-118.
- Peets, J., 2003. The power of iron. Iron production and blacksmithy in Estonia and neighbouring areas in prehistoric period and the Middle Ages., Estonia.
- Pettersson, B., 2007. Kammakeriavfallets spridning på en tidigmedeltida stadsgård i Sigtuna. *Situne Dei*, 7-15.
- Piaskowski, J., 1961. Metallographic Investigations of Ancient Iron Objects from the Territory between the Oder and the Basin of the Vistula River. *Journal of the Iron and Steel Institute* 198, 262-282.
- Piaskowski, J., 1966. Metallographic Examinations of Iron Objects from the Cremation Cemetery at Zadowice, Distr. Kalisz. *Prace i materialy Muzeum Archeologicznego i Etnograficznego w Lodzi (Seria Archeologiczna)* 13, 213-222 and 230 (English summary).
- Pleiner, R., 1959. Metallographische Untersuchungen von vor- und frühgeschichtlichen eisernen Gegenständen aus der Tschechoslowakei. *Stahl und Eisen* 79, 294-298.

- Rinman, S., 1782. *Försök til järnets historia, med tillämpning för slögder och handtwerk*. Petter Hesselberg, Stockholm, Sweden.
- Shugar, A., Notis, M., Limata, L., Wong, D., Hutapea, P., Rubin, H., 2006. Early Chinese scissors and shears: category, design and shape: a metallurgical study, 34th International Symposium on Archaeometry. Centro de Estudios Borjanos, Zaragoza, Spain, pp. 237-244.
- Sjöbeck, A., 2016. Textilhantverk i det äldsta Sigtuna. *Situne Dei*, 40-51.
- Swedenborg, E., 1923. *Mineralriket: Om järnet och de i Europa vanligast vedertagna järnframställningssätten ... Swedish translation of Swedenborg 1734 by Hjalmar Sjögren*. Wahlström & Widstrand, Stockholm, Sweden.
- Söderberg, A., 2006. Om två metallurgiska processer knutna till vikingatidens betalningsväsende. *Situne Dei*, 65-80.
- Söderberg, A., 2011. Eyvind Skáldaspillir's silver – refining and standards in pre-monetary economies in the light of finds from Sigtuna and Gotland. *Situne Dei*, 5-34.
- Söderberg, A., Gustafsson, N.B., 2007. Från prestigevarugjutning till myntning - Tidigmedeltida metallurgi i kvarteret Trädgårdsmästaren, Sigtuna. *Situne Dei*, 17-40.
- Tesch, S., 1990. *Makt och människor i kungens Sigtuna - Sigtunautgrävningen 1988-1990*. Sigtuna Museum, Sigtuna, Sweden.
- Tylecote, R.F., 1990. Scientific examination and analysis of iron objects, in: Biddle, M. (Ed.), *Object and Economy in Medieval Winchester*. Oxford University Press, U.K.
- Wagner, D.B., 1990. Ancient carburization of iron to steel: a comment. *Archaeomaterials* 4, 111-117.
- Wallander, A., 2018. Osmundjärn – Inventeringar och analyser av osmundar från arkeologiska undersökningar i Sverige. *Jernkontorets bergshistoriska utskott*, Stockholm, Sweden.
- Wells, H.B., 1973. Knowledge of Spring Steel in Hellenistic Times. *Journal of the Arms and Armour Society* VII, 249-256.
- Wilthew, P., 2000. Metallographic examination of medieval knives and shears, in: Cowgill, J., de Neergaard, M., Griffiths, N. (Eds.), *Knives and Scabbards*. The Boydell Press, Woodbridge, U.K., pp. 62-74.
- Wiss, J., 1948. *A story of shears and scissors*. J. Wiss & Sons.
- Wärmländer, S.K.T.S., Saage, R., Erkers, L., Fröjd, F., Wåhlander, L., Johnsson, P., Carlsson, E., Grandin, L., Eliasson, A., 2018. Amuletringar snarare än ämnesjärn: metallografisk analys tyder på ojämn materialkvalitet hos vendeltida järnringar från Åselby i Stora Tuna, Dalarna. *Fornvännen* 113, 1-6.
- Wärmländer, S.K.T.S., Söderberg, A., 2019. Hollow comb rivets made from strip-drawn copper wire and two possible antler draw plates from 11th–12th c. Sigtuna, Sweden. *Fornvännen* 114, 88-99.
- Wärmländer, S.K.T.S., Zori, D., Byock, J., Scott, D.A., 2010. Metallurgical findings from a Viking Age chieftain's farm in Iceland. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 37, 2284-2290.
- Zavjalov, V.I., Terekhova, N.N., in press. Technological traditions in the blacksmith's craft of ancient Rus'. *Acta Archaeologica*.

Tables

Table 1. Compositions (in atomic percent) of the martensitic phase and the silicon-based inclusions observed in the blade sample from shears-2 shown in Fig. 6.

	Fe	O	Si	Ca	Al	K
Martensite-phase	100					
Silicon-based inclusions	17.7	44.0	23.8	5.7	6.6	2.2

Table 2. Material properties of the different parts of the two analysed shears.

	Blade	Arm	Bow	Trace metals
Shears-1 (#27182)	Ferritic core (<0.02 % C; ~130 HV ₂₀₀) Ferrite + pearlite (0.14 % C; ~210 HV ₂₀₀)	Ferrite, some Widmanstätten structure	Large-grain ferrite	No trace elements detected by SEM-EDS.
Shears-2 (#23276)	Martensite (0.4 % - 0.5 % C; ~890 HV ₂₀₀) Some pearlite Some ferrite	Ferrite (~130 HV ₂₀₀) Pearlite + ferrite with Widmanstätten structure (0.5 % C; ~240 HV ₂₀₀)	Small-grain ferrite Pearlite + ferrite with Widmanstätten structure	No trace elements detected by SEM-EDS.

Figures

Fig. 1. Schematic figure of Medieval single-bow shears and their terminology.
Drawing by SW based on Cowgill et al. (2000).

Fig. 2. The two studied single-bow shears, excavated from the block Trädgårdsmästaren in central Sigtuna, Sweden, dated to the 11th – 12th c. Left: shears-1. Right: shears-2. Photographs by SW.

Fig. 3. Microstructure photographs of etched samples from one of the arms (A, B) and the bow (C, D) of shears-1. Photographs by AH.

Fig. 4. Microstructure photographs of etched samples from one of the blades of shears-1. C and D show close-up images of regions shown in A and B, respectively. Photographs by AH.

Fig. 5. Microstructure photographs of etched samples from one of the arms (A, B), the bow (C), and one of the blades (D) of shears-2. Photographs by AH.

Fig. 6. SEM image of the blade sample from shears-2, showing a martensitic structure with silicon-based inclusions. Magnification 1500x. Image by SW.